

Experimental Musical Instruments: From Inventors to Innovative Communities¹

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Abstract

Experimental musical instruments have shaped musical culture from early acoustic innovations to contemporary digital systems. This article outlines key historical and technological developments, with emphasis on recent digital instruments and the communities that sustain them. It traces a shift from individual invention toward collaborative, infrastructure-based practice and highlights emerging concerns around accessibility, sustainability, and the preservation of experimental knowledge in contemporary musical instrument design.

Keywords: experimental musical instruments, nime, musical performance, musicology

Every musical instrument has experimental origins. Experimentation with the acoustics of materials and techniques for producing sound led to the invention and refinement of the cultural artifacts we call musical instruments. Archaeological evidence suggests that humans were already experimenting with music-making technology in early prehistory, tens of thousands of years ago (Conard, Malina, and Münzel 2009). Experimental instruments offer musicians access to unconventional sounds and new means of musical expression. New instruments necessitate the invention of alternative playing techniques and fresh approaches to performance. They can stimulate the creativity of musicians to develop new musical forms. In this brief article, I introduce a few examples of experimental music technology, focusing on recent developments relevant to the current situation.

The publication of Athanasius Kircher's "Musurgia Universalis" (Kircher 1650) in the mid-17th century is an early landmark of innovative musical technology. Kircher's book is replete with fascinating reports and ideas for musical experiments: systems for generative composition, musical automata, an aeolian harp played by the wind, a cat organ employing a chorus of living cats to be played using a keyboard, and many other marvels. More recently, the conceptually innovative oeuvre of John Cage has exerted a profound influence on contemporary musical culture (Nyman 1974). Cage employed radios, turntables, seashells, amplified cacti, household items, toy instruments, prepared pianos, compositional strategies involving chance procedures and unconventional scores, and radically reconsidered the roles of composer, performer, and listener.

Technological innovation accelerated in the twentieth century, and music technology was no exception. Among the many new instruments, some notable examples are the Theremin, a pioneering electronic instrument played without physical contact, and the

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voltage-controlled analog modular synthesizers initially developed by Hugh Le Caine, Robert Moog, and others (Pinch and Trocco 2004). Musical experimentation with digital electronics and programmable computers began in approximately the same era (Roads 1996). These developments have continued to affect the evolution of a wide range of new musical forms to the present time.

By the 1990s, digital computation was used widely for music-making tasks ranging from audio synthesis to multi-track sequencing, recording, editing, and mastering in studio production. The growing interest in computer music and the increasing power and accessibility of portable computers led to the personal computer being employed as a tool for music-making. With the "laptop performance" of the nineties, the laptop itself was adopted as a "musical instrument" for live performance. The situation begged the question: "How to play the computer?" Experimental works began to explore devices known as "musical interfaces" for linking expressive human action with digital audio synthesis (Paradiso 1997). Researchers identified an overlap between computer-mediated musical performance and the field of human-computer interaction. This led to the workshop on "New Interfaces for Musical Expression" (NIME) at the ACM CHI'2001 conference in Seattle (Poupyrev et al. 2001).

NIME became an annual conference, now in its twenty-fourth year, and a leading venue for research on new musical instruments consisting of academic presentations and discussions, practical demonstrations, live performances, and artistic installations (NIME 2026). NIME topics of continuing interest include:

- Novel controllers, interfaces, and instruments
- Augmented and hyper-instruments
- Technologies for collaborative and mobile music-making
- Sensor and actuator technologies, including haptics and force feedback devices
- The relationship between gesture and music and mapping strategies
- Accessible design
- Musical applications of robotics and machine learning
- Analyses of music technology's philosophical, artistic, cultural, and social impact

Many experimental digital musical instruments barely escape research labs for a few performances at avant-garde venues. New digital musical instruments that have been commercialised, such as the Yamaha Tenori-on, the Reactable, and the ROLI Seaboard, have yet to enjoy a cultural impact comparable to the electric guitar or the synthesizer. On the other hand, while less visible, researchers and developers have created novel infrastructure for making digital musical instruments that includes Pd, the Pure Data visual programming language, OSC, the Open Sound Control musical network protocol, and Bela, an open-source embedded platform for interactive and real-time audio systems, to list just a few examples. Such tools democratise music technology experimentation, enabling a vital and growing scene of experimental do-it-together music technology innovators and artists. Hence, the activity of NIME and related research and artistic communities has stimulated and educated a substantial population of knowledgeable digital luthiers and musicians.

Once the domain of geniuses, the systematic invention of experimental music instruments is now a central concern of a sizeable international multidisciplinary group of

research musicians, engineers, and designers that spans academic and artistic communities of practice. The range of their creative activity has broadened to include the development of shared platforms and design methodologies in addition to empirical and theoretical studies of performance with new musical instruments.

It is difficult to know what future experimental musical instruments will look like. However, imagining how this innovative community may continue to evolve is interesting. While musical experimentation has historically had few boundaries, activity at the current frontiers of technology is highly concentrated in economically wealthy areas of the world. In the future, music technology innovators could benefit by listening to neglected voices to become more culturally and socially diverse. The rapid pace of innovation causes many musical inventions to be forgotten after a few demonstrations or performances. In the future, a digital musical instrument repository would allow inventors to archive and share their designs, code, data, and rich multimedia documentation (McPherson et al. 2016). Future innovators will likely adopt sustainable practices that respect the planet's environment and limited resources. Finally, experimental musical instrument innovation will likely resist becoming a mere servant of commerce but continue to be driven by human aspirations to explore technological change in the embodied context of real-time live musical performance.

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